

ON THE PHONOLOGICAL STRUCTURE OF LOANWORDS FROM ARABIC AND PERSIAN LANGUAGES (BASED ON MATERIALS FROM THE KARAKALPAK AND TURKMEN LANGUAGES)

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the commonalities and differences in the phonological structure of words borrowed from Arabic and Persian into the Karakalpak and Turkmen languages.

The morpheme occupies a special place among linguistic units. It is a semantic-morphological unit. The morpheme is the smallest meaningful part of a word; beyond this, a word can only be divided phonetically into syllables and phonemes. In Turkic languages, including Karakalpak and Turkmen, morphemes are functionally and semantically divided into **root morphemes** and **affix morphemes**. Structurally, they are distinguished as simple and compound morphemes. Issues regarding the phonemic structure of morphemes are essential for morphonology.

There are two different opinions regarding the evolution of the structure and phonemic composition of root morphemes in Turkic languages. Proponents of the first view—V.V. Radlov, N.A. Batmanov, V.L. Kotvich, J. Deny, N.A. Baskakov, and others—believe that the earliest root morphemes consisted of a **consonant + vowel + consonant** syllable, from which other variations emerged. Proponents of the second view—A.N. Kononov, A.M. Shcherbak, E.V. Sevortyan, A.A. Zayonchkovsky, B.M. Yunusaliev, and others—argue that root morphemes were originally open syllables consisting of a vowel, followed later by the development of structures such as consonant+vowel, vowel+consonant, and consonant+vowel+consonant [1: 24].

In root morphemes of the **consonant + vowel + consonant + consonant** type borrowed from Arabic and Persian into Karakalpak and Turkmen, the final consonant often drops out in Karakalpak but is preserved in written Turkmen. For example:

- **Karakalpak:** *dos(t), qas(t), ras(t)*.
- **Turkmen:** *dost, kast, rast*.

In Karakalpak, the phoneme /t/ only reappears when these words are declined or take possessive suffixes: *dostim, qastıń, dostıma*, etc. However, the phoneme /t/ does not reappear in the word *ras* when possessive suffixes are added. We believe this is likely due to the addition of a prosthetic vowel at the beginning of the word *ras*. Because a prosthetic vowel is added, the

number of syllables in its structure changes, and it no longer requires further changes when taking suffixes.

In Turkmen, the final /t/ in *dost* and *kast* is preserved in writing. No additional phonemes are added during declension or possession because, in Turkmen, affixes starting with a vowel are attached directly to words ending in a consonant: *dostym*, *kastyň*, *dostuma*, *dostumyz*, etc.

B. Weyisov notes that the occurrence of two consecutive consonants in monosyllabic words is rare in Turkmen. Therefore, loanwords ending in /-st/ like *pest*, *dest*, *mest*, *rast*, *sust* were originally adopted into Turkmen with the final /t/ dropped [2: 86]. For example: *Pis pisi tapar*, *suw – pesi*. However, when word-forming suffixes are added, the dropped /t/ reappears: *ras – rastlamak*, *mest – mes*, *messana*, *pest – pes*, *peşsáy*, etc. As seen here, the addition of the /t/ phoneme is most clearly observed in the word *rast*.

However, in the *Explanatory Dictionary of the Turkmen Language (2016)*, the final consonant /t/ is preserved in the words *rast* (adverb), *dest* (noun), and *sust* (adjective). The use of a prosthetic vowel before the word *rast* occurs in spoken language and in verbal forms. For example: *raslamak* – to correct oneself/take a breath; *rastlamak* – to confirm.

There are other types of root morphemes in Karakalpak and Turkmen that emerged through internal and external factors during historical development. Internally, they arose from affix morphemes merging so closely with root morphemes that they became inseparable; these can be identified through etymological analysis. Externally, changes in phonological structure occurred due to borrowings from Arabic, Persian, Russian, and other languages (e.g., *parta*, *qálem*, *respublika*, *miyman*, *mádeniyat*).

N.A. Baskakov writes: "In Turkic languages, root morphemes are limited by specific sequences of phonemes... some languages have added new phonemes, such as /ä/, while in others, vocalism was shortened due to the influence of substrate languages" [3: 186]. Indeed, the phoneme /á/ was added to the vocalism system of Karakalpak and Turkmen during the second stage of development through Arabic influence. Modern Karakalpak has nine vowel phonemes: /a, á, o, ó, u, ú, ı, i, e/. These are contrasted based on tongue height (open-closed), tongue position (back-front), and lip roundedness.

The vowel sounds in Karakalpak differ from Turkmen in both number and articulation [5: 26]. Turkmen has 18 vowel phonemes: /a, o, ö, u, ü, y, i, e, ä/, each appearing in short and long forms. This length distinction serves a phonemic (meaning-distinguishing) function. While some scholars identify 16 vowels, A. Annanurov and S. Kurenov identify 18: nine long (/a:, o:, u:, ü:, y:, i:, ö:, e:, ä:/) and nine short (/a, o, ö, u, ü, y, i, e, ä/) [6: 30].

In Karakalpak, vowel length is not phonemic. "In Karakalpak, the long or short pronunciation of a sound is not used to convey semantic meaning; it may vary only based on phonetic context" [5: 28].

According to the horizontal position of the tongue

Türkmen tilinde (In Turkmen):	Qaraqalpaq tilinde (In Karakalpak):
Front row (Alynky hatar): i, ü, e, ö, ä.	Front (Til aldy): e.
Middle row (Ortaky hatar): y.	Central (Til ortasy): i, á, ó, ú.
Back row (Yzky hatar): u, o, a.	Back (Til arty): a, o, u, ı.

According to the vertical position of the tongue

Türkmen tilinde (In Turkmen):	Qaraqalpaq tilinde (In Karakalpak):
High (Ýokary galyş): i, u, ü.	High / Close (Kóterińki): ı, u, ú, i, e.
Mid (Ortaky galyş): e, o, ö, y.	Mid (Orta kóterińki): o, ó.
Low (Yzky galyş): ä, a.	Low / Open (Túsińki): a, á.

Articulatory differences also exist:

- In **Turkmen**, front vowels include /i, ü, e, ö, ä/, whereas in **Karakalpak**, only /e/ is strictly a front vowel (others like /i, á, ü, ö/ are classified as central-front in various systems).
- The tongue height classifications also vary slightly between the two languages.

In Karakalpak, vowel phonemes do not typically occur in sequence. In loanwords like *saat* (hour), *zúraát* (crop), and *sanaat* (industry), although double vowels are written, a consonant is inserted in speech: *saǵat*, *zúrahat*, *sanahat*. Similarly, in Turkmen, double vowels do not usually occur in root morphemes, though they appear in compound nouns like *Shaapbas* or *Hojaili*.

In conclusion, root morphemes consisting of a closed syllable of the **consonant + vowel + consonant + consonant** type are rare in Karakalpak. In contrast, such four-phoneme root structures are more frequently encountered in the Turkmen language..

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